

Where Is All the Data Hiding?

An Analysis of Hosting and Licensing Practices for Hate Speech Datasets

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Abstract

The paper presents first results of a systematic review on datasets created to address the rise of hate speech and related phenomena in online communication, with a specific focus on hosting and licensing practices of these datasets. The analysis shows that while the majority of the 133 datasets has been directly accessible, over half have not been published via dedicated research data repositories, instead being hosted on GitHub. Additionally, almost 45% of the datasets have been released without any accompanying license. Contrary to expectations, the use of licenses and dedicated repositories has not increased over time. Furthermore, while datasets representing languages from the Global South were somewhat less frequently licensed and hosted on dedicated repositories, this trend was not statistically significant. Similarly, the data source itself had little measurable influence on licensing or hosting choices.

Keywords: data sharing; research data management; FAIR; offensive language datasets; hate speech datasets

1 Introduction

Almost a decade ago, the FAIR principles were introduced by Wilkinson et al. (2016) stating that research data should be findable, accessible, interoperable, and reusable. In this paper, we present an ongoing study of datasets

compiled to support approaches and strategies aimed at combating the increasing volume of online hate speech, especially on social media. Over the past ten years, this topic has seen increasing research interest across multiple disciplines. Research in fields such as psychology and the social sciences has focused on understanding human and social behavior, while the natural language processing and machine learning community has concentrated on developing models capable of automatically detecting various forms and nuances of hate speech. Especially the latter research focus has led to the creation of a vast number of datasets for training and evaluating detection and classification models. This paper looks at the publishing practices of more than 130 datasets identified in the first phase of the study including the locations and licenses as well as their association to data source and language. Linguistic expressions of hate speech are multifaceted, with existing datasets differing with regard to diverse aspects such as language, time periods, platforms, events, or regional and cultural contexts. As such, research aimed at developing more robust models, evaluating existing ones, or assessing their generalization capabilities requires access to these diverse datasets.

This paper examines the hosting locations and licenses of about 130 datasets identified during the first phase of the study. The remainder of the paper is organized as follows: Section 2 gives an overview of related work, followed by an outline of the research methodology in Section 3. Section 4 presents the results which are discussed in Section 5. Finally, a summary and outlook are provided in the concluding section.

2 Related Work

Recent research on dataset publishing practices has focused on openness, reproducibility, and accessibility, particularly within the context of open science. A key trend highlighted in reports like the Open Science Indicators (2019–2022) is the steady rise in data sharing and repository use across scientific disciplines (PLOS Blog, 2023), with data repository usage increasing to 28% in 2022 and 75% of articles sharing data overall (PLOS Blog, 2023). Open data policies have played a significant role in promoting data citation and ensuring that datasets are accompanied by comprehensive, quality metadata for future reuse (PLOS Blog, 2023). However, various challenges remain, hindering broader data-sharing practices. Researchers often face prac-

tical hurdles, including legal and ethical uncertainties, technical issues like inconsistent data formats, and difficulties with long-term data archiving (Stuart et al., 2018). In addition, according to the study by Perrier et al. from 2020 spanning over 2,000 records published between 2003 and 2018, many researchers report insufficient time, resources, and expertise for effectively depositing data into public repositories. This not only impacts data quality but also introduces subjective biases in deciding what data is worth sharing (Perrier et al., 2020). Moreover, inadequate infrastructure further hampers research data availability. A lack of strong incentives to share data compounds these issues, limiting progress in open science practices (Perrier et al., 2020).

Most related articles emphasize the critical role of metadata in achieving FAIR principles as it supports discovery, reuse, and compliance (Tedersoo et al., 2021; Stuart et al., 2018). Standardized vocabularies and robust data descriptions have been identified as essential strategies for effective dataset documentation, but balancing these needs with practical constraints remains a challenge for many researchers (Tedersoo et al., 2021). Gomes et al. (2022) identify further key obstacles of researchers, such as lack of time, insufficient technical expertise, and concerns about data misuse, arguing for aligning institutional policies and incentives to encourage data sharing. Their study also highlights the potential benefits, such as enhanced collaboration and increased research impact, that go along with open data practices (Gomes et al., 2022).

The widespread use of platforms like Zenodo and GitHub for dataset publishing, particularly in computational fields, has been an important step in addressing some of the barriers, especially time constraints and technical challenges (Leipzig et al., 2021). Zenodo integrates with GitHub to streamline dataset management, providing automatic DOI generation and version control and ensuring that datasets remain citable and reproducible. This combination could be especially beneficial for maintaining long-term accessibility and facilitating updates to datasets, but also to enhance transparency and foster broader data sharing (GitHub Documentation, 2024).

The relevance of GitHub has been confirmed in a recent related study examining the targets of hate in hate speech datasets (Yu et al., 2024). Using a collection of datasets published between 2012 and 2022, partly overlapping with ours, the authors deduced that 51% of the datasets in their sample were publicly available (i.e., links provided or data available upon request), with GitHub being the dominant platform for dataset distribution (62%). However, issues with dataset access were noted, such as broken links or outdated con-

tact information for dataset requests (Yu et al., 2024). In contrast to Yu et al. (2024), we additionally examine the association between hosting location, the choice of licenses and dataset characteristics such as data source and language.

3 Methodology

This study is part of a larger ongoing study conducting a systematic review of datasets developed in research focused on identifying and combating offensive language including hateful, toxic and abusive speech as well as hate speech with a dedicated focus on annotation quality and the respective guidelines. We chose OpenAlex as the main search entry point due to its broad coverage and sources. More precisely, OpenAlex indexes different types of records (referred to as ‘works’), including datasets, by retrieving information from a range of sources, mainly Microsoft Academic Graph (MAG) and Crossref, as well as a plethora of other resources, including subject-area and institutional repositories like arXiv.org.¹

At the time of conducting the query in July 2024, the OpenAlex index contained more than 250 million scholarly works from over 150,000 sources including non-English languages and the Global South (OpenAlex, 2024), covering between 96% and 99% of publications in Scopus, Web of Science, Semantic Scholar and PubMed for records published between 2012 and 2022 (Hauptka et al., 2024, p. 6). Additionally, we implemented a snowball sampling approach to increase the dataset coverage, which remains ongoing and is not included in the presented results.

As for the query we used a two-fold approach: A title-only query, which yielded 693 results, was combined with a topic-type query that returned 886 entries.² The following query was used for the title-only query:³

(offensive OR hateful OR toxic OR abusive OR profanity OR "hate speech" OR hatespeech) AND (corpus OR "data set" OR dataset OR collection)

1 <https://help.openalex.org/hc/en-us/articles/24397285563671-About-the-data>

2 <https://github.com/helenamihaljevic/hate-speech-dataset-survey>

3 The same query has also been tested including the abstract, resulting in a GB-size json-file that included a huge amount of false positives.

The two result sets were merged, and duplicates were removed, leaving 1,485 works. These were further filtered based on their primary topic area, retaining only those from the following list, for example, excluding papers from the medical domain: "Computer Science", "Social Sciences", "Business, Management and Accounting", "Arts and Humanities", "Economics, Econometrics and Finance", "Decision Sciences", "Mathematics", "Psychology". After this filtering step, 1,237 works remained. These were further refined by publication year and language, including only works published from 2010 onwards and written in a language the authors are fluent in, specifically English and German. Each of the remaining 1,048 entries was then manually evaluated based on the following inclusion criteria:

1. The dataset is described in a peer-reviewed or at least editorially reviewed publication, including dataset papers and PhD theses, detailing the development process and dataset characteristics.
2. The publication is written in English or German.
3. The dataset is novel (i.e., newly compiled), or an existing dataset has been enriched or expanded with additional annotations or records, including synthetically generated datasets.
4. The dataset contains annotations at the post- or sentence-level, with human involvement in the labeling process. Datasets labeled exclusively by automated systems are excluded, as were papers focusing solely on dictionary development.
5. The dataset contains annotations addressing at least one of the following phenomena: offensive, hateful, toxic, abusive or profane content. Entries focusing on trolling or political violence were excluded, as these topics were not systematically covered by our query.
6. The dataset is accessible, meaning at least one of the following conditions is met:
 - The paper provides a link to the dataset location, and the repository actually contains the data.
 - The dataset can be found in a common repository (e.g., Zenodo, GitHub) and can be found via a simple search using the dataset's name or the author's names.
 - The dataset is provided on the authors' website.
 - The dataset can be found via a general internet search using the dataset's name or the paper's title.

- The dataset authors provide a dedicated description on how to access the dataset (e.g., contact the authors), either in the publication or the repository.

If the entry failed to meet any of these criteria, it was excluded from the analysis. During this phase, we also removed 292 near-duplicates (e.g., different versions of the same dataset). Furthermore, at least 85 entries were excluded because the dataset was not actually available. This includes cases where the dataset has been announced in a repository but has not been made available, or only a sample has been provided. Since failing any of the above criteria was grounds for exclusion, not all criteria were systematically examined for every entry, meaning this number only shows the bottom line of datasets excluded by this criterion. In total, 133 entries met all the inclusion criteria and were retained for the subsequent analysis of hosting and licensing practices in this topic area.⁴ For each paper-dataset pair, we determined where the data has been published and which license has been chosen, if any. Moreover, we used information on the dataset source (e.g., Twitter), dataset language, and dataset type (e.g., text) to assess the relationship between dataset provision and licensing on the one hand and these dataset characteristics on the other.

4 Results

The datasets included for the analysis were published between 2016 and 2024, showing an upward trend in the number of datasets released per year (Fig. 1)⁵, resulting in almost one third of the datasets being released in the last 1.5 years and thus had not been included in prior research on the topic. The primary topic category⁶ for almost all datasets in the sample (128 out of 133) is “Automated Detection of Hate Speech and Offensive Language”, which can at least partly be attributed to the data collection method used in this study.

4 The reserach dataset is available on Zenodo: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14781288>

5 The year 2024 includes only data for the first half of the year, explaining the smaller number of datasets in that year.

6 Topics are assigned automatically by OpenAlex based on available information such as title and abstract. The primary topic is the work’s highest-scoring topic; for more detail see <https://docs.openalex.org/api-entities/topics>.

Fig. 1 Distribution of the publication year in the sample (absolute numbers per year)

Most datasets were not published in a dedicated research data repository (Fig. 2); instead, they were made available on GitHub⁷, a platform primarily used for developing and sharing code. This reflects the research context of the publications, as most datasets are developed with the goal of training machine learning models; thus, the datasets are typically accompanied by code used for model training and evaluations. Fewer than 30% of the datasets were published in repositories specifically designed for sharing research data and publications, with Zenodo being the most frequently used. This proportion slightly decreases when considering datasets released from 2023 onwards, with only 13 of 42 datasets published in dedicated research data repositories. Other locations include Google Drive (3), Figshare (4), Kaggle (5), Clarin (3), and Hugging Face (4) as well as personal websites (4). Seven datasets are published in more than one hosting location (Fig. 2), typically including GitHub and a research data repository. Another seven datasets are only available upon request from the authors. The general findings, especially the dominance of GitHub, are in line with Yu et al. (2024); however, in their sample, repositories like Zenodo account for only 5% of the datasets.

Fig. 2 Distribution of datasets across platforms and repositories (multiple counts for datasets published on multiple hosting locations)

7 <https://github.com/>

Besides the findability and hosting of a dataset, another important factor for its reuse is the license assigned to it. Almost half of the datasets in the sample (59 out of 133) do not include any license information. Among the 74 datasets that do specify a license, Creative Commons (CC) licenses are the most common, with 33 datasets made available under a CC BY license, ten under a CC BY-SA license, followed by CC BY-NC-SA and CCo licenses with six and three datasets, respectively. Other common licenses stem from the open source domain, with Apache 2.0, GPL 3.0, and MIT license. Additionally, some datasets, all of which are released on GitHub, are assigned custom licenses (Fig. 3). Three datasets come with conflicting license information (e.g., CC BY and CCo) on different hosting locations (Fig. 3).

Fig. 3 Distribution of licenses (multiple counts for datasets with multiple license choices)

A substantial portion of datasets without license is published on GitHub (35), with 49% solely published there, while 38% were published on Zenodo only (nine out of 24). Also, data available only upon request from the authors have no publicly specified license.

We examined the association between the license and the repository (see Fig. 4) using a Chi-squared test of independence. After grouping the data (license specified/ license not specified; repository: dedicated research data repositories / software oriented repositories / other) ensuring each dataset is only counted once by using the stricter license (e.g., CC BY when also CCo was given) and preferring the research data repository in case of multiple hosting locations, the analysis revealed a statistically significant relationship between the two variables ($\chi^2 = 8.48$, $df = 2$, $p < 0.05$), indicating that the distributions of the two variables are not independent. As expected, the observed differences suggest that research data oriented repositories are more likely to be associated with a license.

To examine potential statistical relationships between dataset characteristics (e.g., dataset source or dataset language) and repository choice or licensing, we conducted further chi-squared tests between these characteristics and repository and license.

Fig. 4 Distribution of datasets with and without specified licences across grouped hosting locations

The distribution of dataset sources followed a long-tail pattern, with 50 datasets originating solely from Twitter but a total of 47 unique sources across the sample. Given this high source diversity, we grouped datasets into three broad categories, namely social media datasets, synthetic datasets (human- or machine-generated), and other datasets (e.g., news forums or Wikipedia comments). This grouping was based on the assumption that synthetic datasets would be accompanied by licenses more often as no terms and conditions from external platforms apply. The chi-squared test results, however, showed no statistically significant relationship between dataset licensing (presence vs. absence of a license) and dataset source. However, a statistically significant relationship was found between repository type (grouped as above) and dataset source ($\chi^2 = 10.71$, $df = 4$, $p < 0.05$), with synthetic datasets being more frequently hosted on software-oriented repositories (Fig. 5)., Nonetheless, caution is needed when interpreting these results, as various groupings of sources would have been suitable, and the significance of statistical relationships depends on how categories are grouped.

Fig. 5 Distribution of grouped hosting locations and grouped data source types

Since we did not extract author affiliation, we used dataset language as a proxy to test the hypothesis that universities in the Global South may have fewer resources to support proper research data management. To examine this, we categorized dataset languages into two broad groups – Global South and Global North. The results indicated a tendency for datasets representing languages from the Global South to be less frequently accompanied by a license and less often provided on dedicated research data repositories. However, this trend did not reach statistical significance, suggesting that while there may be disparities in research data management practices, further investigation is needed to confirm these patterns.

Finally, we hypothesized that the relative use of licenses and dedicated dataset repositories would increase over time. However, our tests did not detect a statistically significant relationship between publication year (with 2016–2018 grouped together) and either of the two variables (grouped as described above).

5 Discussion

The prevalence of GitHub as the primary platform for sharing data is not so surprising, given that most datasets in the sample originate from research in natural language processing and machine learning. The creation of these datasets is closely linked to the development of models for detecting and classifying hate speech and its variations, which typically requires the implementation of code. GitHub, being the presumably most relevant code repository in these communities, serves as a ‘natural’ location to host both the modelling code and the corresponding datasets for training and evaluating, aligning with the workflow practices in this research community.

This aspect, however, must be carefully considered in all conceptual designs and methodologies of data-sharing frameworks. A promising direction to address this challenge involves structuring data repositories in GitHub more systematically. Enhanced organizational practices and tools that facilitate the connectivity and traceability of datasets within GitHub could significantly boost its usability and traceability.

Beyond openness, it is equally important to incorporate the FAIR principles (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable). Embedding these principles into the development and management of repositories on GitHub or

other code platforms would ensure that resources not only remain openly available but also meet the standards necessary for long-term accessibility and scholarly accuracy.

GitHub not only facilitates collaborative software development but also supports the documentation and provision of open-source software. In 2014, GitHub introduced an integration with Zenodo, allowing users to archive GitHub repositories and assign them persistent identifiers (DOIs) for citation and long-term access. This feature enables researchers to preserve specific versions of their software and make it referenceable in academic publications. Additionally, GitHub supports publicizing and citation of research materials from Figshare (Nielsen, 2024; Helling et al., 2022; GitHub Documentation 2024). This shows once again that practical solutions to enhance data and software accessibility already exist within the computing community. However, based on the results of this study, it appears that these tools and interfaces are not yet widely known and adopted.

The finding that nearly half of the datasets were released without any specified license, along with the presence of (at least) three datasets with conflicting license choices, underscores the need to raise awareness about the importance of granting clear licenses to enable legal reuse of datasets. Various factors likely contribute to this issue, including uncertainties regarding the terms of use imposed by original data sources, concerns related to privacy, and the reproduction of hateful or legally forbidden content – particularly for datasets derived from social media. Although, we could not find a significant relationship between the presence and absence of a license and the dataset source. Addressing these uncertainties is essential, as they are likely to become even more relevant with the increasing use of Large Language Models (LLMs) to generate data. Notably, our sample already includes some synthetic datasets reflecting the goal to compile larger semi-automatically labeled data.

The results presented in this study are subject to several limitations. As the study is still ongoing, the sample represents only an excerpt of the full data basis of the systematic review, since the data of the accompanying snowball approach is still subject to analysis. To gain a more comprehensive understanding of data-sharing practices, future work should expand the scope to include a wider range of topics and adopt a broader methodological approach. This could involve combining the analysis of publication practices with insights obtained from surveys or interviews with researchers in the relevant communities.

6 Conclusion and Outlook

This paper demonstrates that data sharing in natural language processing and machine learning communities is largely kept within the code sharing environment and that possibilities for integrating these into data repositories are not yet well adopted in these communities. Also, licenses are still a topic that needs attention from the community in order to support FAIR principles and make the reuse of data possible in a legal manner by explicitly granting reuse rights, thus promoting data reproducibility and interdisciplinary collaboration.

One area that remains unexplored in this study is data decay, the phenomenon of datasets becoming partially or entirely inaccessible over time. For example, assessing how many datasets remain fully accessible, rather than containing partially deleted IDs, would help clarify data-sharing practices – especially for social media data, which is often shared this way due to legal uncertainties. Moreover, it would be interesting to see if there are any correlations between the assigned or missing licenses and the reuse of datasets, as well as geographic regions or journals publishing the respective papers or funding behind the dataset creation.

Furthermore, we have not detected any datasheets for the published datasets, and it would be interesting to explore this systematically in a larger sample. The way datasets are currently provided makes evaluation of different data aspects difficult.

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